

Design Thinking for Effective Collaboration in Agile Teams: A Path towards Business Excellence

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: February

Year: 2020

P-ISSN: 2321-4643

Impact Factor: 3.122

Citation:

Mohanrao, Rashmi.
“Design Thinking for Effective Collaboration in Agile Teams: A Path towards Business Excellence.” *Shanlax International Journal of Management*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2020, pp. 101–06.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3737736>

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Abstract

As development of large and complex projects involving multiple agile teams have become increasingly popular, effective collaboration is critical to ensure priorities and dependencies across the teams are understood and addressed.

This paper is based on Ethnographic Research and Qualitative Observation methods used by the author while working with teams in various consulting and development engagements in insurance and banking organisations over the last decade.

This paper addresses the key challenges and gaps observed by the author and aims to explore the concept of collaboration in software development methodologies like Agile, Lean and Systems thinking. It proposes a framework, based on design thinking that will integrate the key principles of the above methodologies into three stages. The three stages of Initiation, Implementation and Innovation will form an iterative process to be included within a project life cycle. It emphasises representation of stakeholders from Business, cross-functional agile teams and good facilitators to foster collaboration in each of the stages. Author further explores three key dimensions of Priority determination, Effective communication and continuous improvement within the framework.

Keywords: Team collaboration, Systems thinking, Lean, Agile, Design thinking, Communication.

Introduction

With the fast changing global market, organisations need to have a system in place to adapt and deliver products or services not only quicker but also more efficiently than ever before. While agile software development has increasingly become the norm, organisations still struggle to work effectively as a team, especially on large and complex projects involving multiple agile teams.

Collaboration, though not new in the workplace, has become increasingly more important to contribute towards a shared objective within the organisation especially with multiple cross-functional teams and evolving business needs. One of the key focus areas in agile software development is collaboration, as highlighted by two of the values in the Agile Manifesto (M Fowler, 2001), which are ‘Individuals and interactions over processes and tools’ and ‘Customer collaboration over contract negotiation’.

This paper will address the challenges and gaps identified by the author and leverage Systems thinking, Lean principles and agile

methodologies to mitigate the same. A framework based on design thinking is proposed that integrates the key principles of above three methodologies into an iterative process that can be applied to a project lifecycle to strengthen team collaboration. One key success factor is to involve internal stakeholders throughout the process and have a good facilitator to guide in the creation of guidelines, standards and tools for the team to apply. Also a consistent approach towards planning, execution and delivery will go a long way to increase transparency and foster an environment of continuous improvement.

Literature Review

What is Collaboration? It is working together rather than to independently accomplish a task. Collaboration is when a group of people with specialised skillsets contribute and work together as a team to deliver shared objectives.

So, what skills are required for collaboration? Collaboration fundamentally expects willingness to work with others, respect for each other, communicate effectively, be open to new ideas and be able to compliment and provide constructive feedback. Behaviours built on these skills will enable teams to work together and boost team performance, which in turn boosts organisation performance.

As projects get complex and skillsets increasingly specialised, collaboration as a practice becomes more important in a software development environment. The following methodologies show how collaboration is a key factor in their adoption and implementation:

Agile methodology at its core is a collaboration model, which consists of cross-functional teams working in an iterative framework to develop software. From the Agile Manifesto's core values (M Fowler, 2001), the 12 guiding principles for agile software development was derived (Kent M. Beck, 2001), which puts people before processes.

Systems' thinking is a holistic approach to analysis that focuses on the way a system interacts and interrelates with other surrounding systems (Rouse, 2005). The systems thinking approach contrasts with traditional analysis, which studies systems by breaking them down into separate elements. From a software development perspective, System thinking can be used as a method of critical thinking by which teams can collaboratively analyse the interconnections between the different systems to understand a situation or problem for better decision-making.

Lean, originally conceptualised by manufacturing organizations, is a continuous improvement strategy that focuses on eliminating waste and maximising value for customer (Poppendieck, 2002). Lean principles are also relevant to software development, which follows an iterative process, and relies on the collaboration of a group of people with different skillsets to meet the business objectives.

Design thinking, in its simplest form, is a user-centric approach for creating new and innovative ideas and solving problems. It is an iterative, flexible and focused method of collaboration between teams and ideas that bring innovation and not limited to a specific industry or area of expertise. The different stages in the Design Thinking process is as below (J. Brodny, 2017):

- Empathise: Understand the needs of the customer involved.
- Define: Understand and define the problem in customer-centric ways.
- Ideate: Think outside the box to identify solutions
- Prototype: An experimental phase where the aim is to identify the best possible solution by building prototypes
- Test: Developing and testing out the solutions identified.
- Adapt: Learn from failure, Inspect and Adapt to move forward.

Research

This paper is based on Ethnographic Research and Qualitative Observation methods used by the Author while working with teams in various consulting and development projects in companies over the last decade which have led to the below research questions:

Q1. What are the challenges faced by internal stakeholders and facilitators to foster collaboration across multiple agile teams and prevent silos?

Q2. What are the challenges faced by agile teams to collaborate and deliver common project goals?

Methodology

The author has worked with various IT and Business units to deliver projects and customer initiatives. The author has interacted with key stakeholders in the business like the Product Owners, Business SMEs and front line operations in a systems thinking experiment to maximise customer value. Also worked with multiple agile teams and scrum masters to deliver projects in an agile software development environment. The above interactions and resultant observations were gained through face to face communication, meetings, one on one conversations, using collaboration tools like Skype, email and observing the frontline operatives on calls at the contact centres. The author from experience has observed and highlighted the key challenges and gaps that led to the research questions

Q1. Challenges faced by internal stakeholders and facilitators to foster collaboration across multiple agile teams and prevent silos?

Q2. What are the challenges faced by agile teams to collaborate and deliver common project goals?

Analysis & Findings

The Author while working with teams in various consulting and development engagements in large Banking and insurance companies over the last decade has observed challenges that have led to the research questions. The analysis and findings are as below:

Q1. Challenges faced by internal stakeholders and facilitators to foster collaboration across multiple agile teams and prevent silos?

- Limiting focus on a single methodology/framework
Each functional unit or team was focused on only one methodology or framework that was not consistent across teams.
- Lack of consistent approach to project lifecycle
Most of the focus in the project lifecycle was on implementation that created issues not addressed properly during initiation and the learnings from retrospective and feedback was not always incorporated into the lifecycle
- Lack of common guidelines across teams
Guidelines were usually discussed during orientation but there was no central knowledge repository for reference to foster common understanding of processes within and across teams

Q2. What are the challenges faced by agile teams to collaborate and deliver common project goals?

- Lack of clarity on prioritisation
Lack of common understanding of shared project objectives. Prioritisation matrix not understood across multiple teams. This was primarily due to the fact that each team/unit traditionally operated in silo and focussed only on unit delivery
- Lack of communication

Communication was ineffective due to focus on individual goals rather than team goals.

- Lack of drive for Continuous improvement

It was found that though the team performed retrospectives, follow through actions were lacking or forgotten with other project priorities where the team missed out on learning opportunities.

The Author proposes the framework depicted in the figure 1 below to address the first research question and its challenges:

Q1.Challenges faced by internal stakeholders and facilitators to foster collaboration across multiple agile teams and prevent silos?

- Limiting focus on a single methodology/framework
- Lack of consistent approach to project lifecycle
- Lack of common guidelines across teams

The framework is based on design thinking principles and leverages key principles from System thinking, Agile and Lean methodologies and creates a three stage iterative process to be applied to the project lifecycle with the involvement and collective understanding of multiple agile teams, stakeholders and facilitators within the delivery programme. Additionally, a good facilitator across the three stages is key to curb the tendency for team members to resort to familiar patterns and assist in removing obstacles and setting guidelines for working practices and to encourage self-organisation within the team.

Figure 1 Design Thinking Framework for Collaboration within Project Lifecycle

Systems thinking will address exploration and definition of problems and forms the Initiation stage based on the design thinking principles of Empathy and Definition; Agile will collectively identify and build a solution in the software development environment and forms the Implementation stage based on the design thinking principles of Ideation and experimentation; Lean will enable test and adapt, to learn from failure, measuring the right things and strive to continuously improve forms the Innovation stage based on the design thinking principles of test and adapt to learn from failures.

The Author proposes the framework depicted in the figure 2 below to address the second research question and its challenges:

Q2.what are the challenges faced by agile teams to collaborate and deliver common project goals?

- Lack of clarity on prioritisation
- Lack of communication
- Lack of drive for Continuous improvement

Figure 2 Three Dimensions Adaptation of the Framework

Figure: 2 above gives an overview of how the dimensions of priority determination, communication and continuous improvement can be achieved by adapting the three stage iterative process as defined by the framework in figure: 1 as part of the project lifecycle.

A project/programme usually consists of multiple agile teams and stakeholders such as business users and product owners across different functional units. One of the key objectives of the framework proposed is to bring together all the teams involved and ensure stakeholder buy-in and representation in each of the stages. A good facilitator like the scrum master or agile coach will ensure the participation of the relevant teams and stakeholders.

The first dimension is Priority determination. Understanding the priority of the different items within a project/program across multiple agile teams is critical to its success. This process will bring together representatives from each of the agile teams, stakeholders and the facilitator to collectively explore, define and prioritise the problems. This process is key to bring about a common understanding or shared projectgoal.

The second dimension is effective communication. It is critical to have the right team culture; creating a team manifesto is the first step towards involving and engaging all the team members to respect each other and promote transparency within the team. In addition to this, establishing processes, guidelines, and good working practices and establishing creative spaces to promote greater interaction will contribute towards common understanding and enhanced team morale. This clubbed with the right methodology and tools will help the teams implement and deliver the project goals.

The third dimension is Continuous improvement. It is critical to learn from failure and to foster an environment of inspect and adapt along with proper appreciation and constructive feedback for work done. It is also important to measure the right things from which we can identify the improvement areas and define action items. Action items need to be incorporated into the subsequent iterations of the project lifecycle to be prioritised to reap the benefits of learning.

Conclusion

Purpose of the paper is to address the research questions and propose a framework to mitigate key challenges observed by the author during his interactions with Business and IT teams in an agile software development environment over a decade.

Faced by teams to collaborate effectively and how we can use design thinking to integrate key principles of systems thinking, lean and agile to create an iterative three staged process of Initiation, Implementation and Innovation to be adapted as part of the project lifecycle with emphasis on representation of stakeholders from Business, Cross functional agile teams and a good facilitator to foster collaboration in each of the stages. The framework further explores the dimensions of Priority determination, Effective communication and continuous improvement within a project/ programme development cycle.

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